

Author: Mr David de Haan, Ironbridge Gorge Museum Trust

Email address: david.dehaan@ironbridge.org.uk

Keywords: World Heritage Site, Ironbridge Gorge, industrial heritage, blast furnace, wrought iron

Abstract

Running an Industrial World Heritage Site: A prominent example – Ironbridge Gorge.

Ironbridge in the heart of England is universally recognised as the birthplace of the Industrial Revolution, especially in ironmaking. The peak of invention and activity lasted only around 100 years from 1709 to 1810, after which the area began to decline when raw materials were worked out and further developments favoured regions with better communications, especially those that could be reached by rail. A few large factories survived through into the 20th century, but most of the remains of the earlier period had fallen into decay. Fortunately there was little economic growth to replace it so it survived, and 40 years ago in 1967 the Ironbridge Gorge Museum Trust was set up to restore, preserve and interpret the remains of what later was to become the first industrial World Heritage Site – the Ironbridge Gorge.

Ironbridge in 1801

Derelict Tile Factory, 1970s

Restored China factory, 1984

The Museum is not funded by local, regional or national government. Instead, the Trust is a private organisation that covers 75% of its daily running costs by getting visitors to pay for admission and buying souvenirs. The rest comes from grants that can vary from year to year. In 1968 a government endowment of 5.5million Euros provided a revenue stream from the interest that could only be used for ongoing maintenance of the key monuments, with 1.5million of it made available for a major conservation programme in the 1990s. But historic monuments are expensive to restore and often after the work is done there is little visible on the surface to show for it. Old factories are also much more expensive to look after than modern buildings, but we have had considerable success over the years in raising money for large restoration projects. In almost all cases these funds are only for capital works. The hard part is covering the running costs. The trick, however, is to interpret these industrial sites in a way that attracts and excites visitors and we welcome around 300,000 of them each year. We have to find ways that make historical processes interesting to today's visitors, in subjects that are outside their everyday experience.

An 1832 blast furnace, (left) derelict in 1963, (centre) as part of the Museum in 1980, and (right) being conserved in 1993

With 200 staff and 150 volunteers today the Trust manages 34 historic sites spread over an area of 1500 hectares (6 square miles). Within these sites are 7 blast furnaces ranging from the 17th to the 19th century, and 4 complete factories covering the manufacture of cast iron, wall and floor tiles, porcelain, and clay tobacco pipes. There is also an Open Air Museum with mines, brickworks and the world's only producing wrought iron works. The paper looks at some of the key challenges there are when industrial processes are demonstrated using original equipment.

Blists Hill. Colliery winding engine demonstrated in steam on a daily basis.

Blists Hill Wrought iron rolling mill

We all know that the demonstrating of historic machinery is an inherently destructive process, but agree that this is acceptable because of the enhanced educational value, as long as a type sample is preserved somewhere in the country. The trouble is that there is still no national database of all machinery 'in captivity', so what may have been an ordinary every-day survivor in the 1960s could have become the only one of its kind today – and one that is being used, maintained, repaired, and thereby altered. Preserved working locomotives are the obvious example, where during their working life every part has been replaced so that nothing of the original remains. Further work has to be done to create reliable lists of *unaltered* machines. Currently this type of information can only be gathered by consulting widely with one's colleagues – and that required a considerable amount of accumulated experience that only comes with time. A UK national maritime register of historic ships is being compiled, and in the past we have undertaken a listing of Social & Industrial History collections in our region, but it does not cover the whole country.

A working machine helps us not only explain the conditions people used to work in, but also the status of the engineer, the way our lives changed with the availability of cheap goods, the wages they earned and their position in society. In short, the history of technology is also the history of people, and people are often far more interesting than a piece of machinery. To an ever declining number of older visitors the working engine reminds them of their early years, but to many younger ones we have to go back to basics and even explain what that black stuff is they are burning in the boiler. So the working machine is the key that opens the door on a fascinating past. Nowadays you can still go underground in 'museum' mines, which are vividly brought to life by ex-miners. But what will happen in 20 years time when the current generation of retired miners are too old? Will we have any engineers who know how to look after the old machines?

Let's take a closer look at one example. Throughout the 19th century wrought iron was an important material. The last working factory closed down in 1976 and the Ironbridge Gorge Museum acquired much of the equipment and re-erected it at the Blists Hill open air museum. We invited the recently-retired workmen to train a new generation in the largely manual process, passing on their trade secrets that were only shared as part of a long apprenticeship. The process is dramatic and visually exciting, and of great interest to visitors standing a safe distance away on the viewing platform. But wrought iron has little market value when steel is less than a tenth of the cost. Our hope was that we could make this special material for conservation purposes, for the restoration of 18th and 19th century decorative metalwork. But the furnaces eat money!

Blists Hill Wrought Ironworks

When they were rolling metal on a daily basis the workmen got a feel for quality, were able to make a consistently good product, often through an acquired knowledge of the correct colour and shape of the flame, and how the material felt. That's repeatable where you can run a historic process on a daily basis, but the demand for this very expensive material is relatively small, so the rolling mills are only operated once a month. The equipment is heated up from cold, run for a few hours, and allowed to cool down. As a result the furnaces expand and contract when they used to be kept alight for months on end. This causes failures that are expensive to repair and adds to the commercial cost of the material. We no longer puddle iron from scratch. Instead we re-roll scrap anchor chains, but that means we do not control the original quality. The conservation blacksmith who buys this expensive material deserves a quality product, but manufacture on this small scale means the demonstrators never gain the cumulative experience that is so important.

How can we solve this dilemma? Firstly we need to know there is a reasonable demand. Then we need to train a new generation of people to maintain the equipment and another team to work the metal. Only if there is continuous production can there be controllable quality. But only if there is sufficient demand can we have sufficient production. The one staff member who has the relevant experience is now too old to do the physical work. He can only describe and direct the process. He can't do the job himself. To save a working process like this we need a lot of money, reliable machinery and the skill of specialist craftsmen. If that investment is not found soon the process will be lost and the restoration of historic wrought iron with the correct material will be impossible. We know of no other producer anywhere in the world, and yet this vital factory only survives in a privately owned museum which depends on visitors paying to keep it going. This is a case for national lobbying by conservationists, historic building experts and heritage groups before it is too late.